

The Effect of Teamwork and Workload on The Quality of Human Resources Mediated by Work Motivation

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine (1) the effect of teamwork on the quality of human resources in the Deputy for Industry and Investment; (2) the effect of workload on the quality of human resources; (3) the effect of teamwork on work motivation at the Deputy; (4) the effect of workload on work motivation in the Deputy; (5) the influence of work motivation on the quality of HR; (6) the influence of teamwork on the quality of HR through the mediation of work motivation; and (7) the effect of workload on the quality of HR through the mediation of work motivation. The results showed that teamwork positively affected the quality of employees. Teamwork has a positive effect on employee motivation. With this increase in influence, it can be conveyed that strong cooperation is motivated by high teamwork spirit.

1. Introduction

Competition in the business world is currently increasingly competitive; companies and government agencies are expected to be able to manage and regulate their human resources effectively and efficiently in order to survive and grow so that the goals of companies and government agencies can be achieved. One of the efforts to increase the productivity of human resources is mostly made by government institutions, one of which is by improving the quality of Human Resources (HR), which is an important factor in improving the performance and achievements of employees of an organization or agency.

The quality of the State Civil Apparatus (In Indonesia, it is called ASN) is currently still far from what the government expects, in addition to the lack of expertise, motivation, and cooperation in

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serving the community are still very low. According to Anggoro (2017) argued that the low quality of ASN can be seen from the educational background they have; from the total number of Civil Servants (PNS) in Indonesia, 4.475 million, 64% of whom only have administrative skills, 37% are teachers and 4.43% are health workers. Besides that, Anggoro (2017) also said that many ASNs think they are rulers even though ASNs are public servants, so it is the mentality of ASN like this that must be addressed; ASN must have a hospitality spirit, not a ruler's spirit.

At this time, every organization is required to compete with other organizations or agencies, either in the same field or in a different field. One of the determinants of competition in an organization is the quality of the human resources in it. Human Resources (HR) and agencies/organizations are two things that are difficult to separate. This is because the quality of its human resources determines the success of an organization or agency, so the agency must pay attention to the quality and productivity of its employees in order to improve employee performance and simultaneously is expected to have an impact on improving the performance and productivity of the agency.

Agencies do not only need qualified and skilled employees. Agencies really need employees who can work harder and desire to achieve optimal results per agency goals. Institutional support for the capabilities possessed by employees is important, considering that the agency environment, both internal and external, will always experience continuous change. Factors that affect the quality of HR, according to Berliana (2014) namely internal factors, namely what is owned by employees included in this factor are education, skills, expertise, and added value, and external factors, namely what is outside the workforce that can be a stimulus for the workforce.

One solution to increase productivity in an agency is to restructure the organization to increase competitive advantage in the era of globalization and as a demand for a change from the old (manual) management system to an integrated management system. The hope is to improve services to the community by placing human resources following their competencies.

Restructuring or renewal efforts in government institutions are usually related to employees (both ASN and Non-ASN employees). The challenge faced by government institutions is that implementing bureaucratic services tends to be convoluted. Each stakeholder has different interests from one another, so the performance measures of public organizations in the eyes of stakeholders are also different so that employees can respond to changes faster. It is necessary to improve the performance of employees in government institutions in order to be able to work professionally. Besides that,

The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy of the Republic of Indonesia / Agency for Tourism and Creative Economy or abbreviated Kemenparekraf RI / Baparekraf RI, is a ministry within the Government of Indonesia in charge of tourism affairs. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is under and responsible to the President. The objectives and responsibilities of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy/Tourism and Creative Economy Agency are how to build and develop 13 tourism business sectors and 16 creative economy sub-sectors by coordinating all relevant government agencies both at the center and in the regions.

The current condition of the Indonesian Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy/Baparekraf RI is a newly formed institution (Ministry of Tourism & Creative Economy Agency), so acceleration is needed in preparing competent human resources. Many new recruits have not received training and understanding related to tourism because most of them are from general majors. In addition, the development theme, which is also the Vision of the elected President in the 2020-2024 national development carried out through 7 (seven) development agendas which are National Priorities (PN) in the 2020-2024 RPJMN IV are as follows;

- PN 1. Strengthening Economic Resilience for Quality and Equitable Growth
- PN 2. Developing Regions to Reduce Gaps
- PN 3. Improving Qualified and Competitive Human Resources
- PN 4. Mental Revolution and Cultural Development
- PN 5. Strengthening Infrastructure to Support Economic Development and Basic Services
- PN 6. Building the Environment, Improving Disaster Resilience and Climate Change
- PN 7. Strengthening the Stability of Polhukhankam and Transforming Public Services

Kemenparekraf RI/Baparekraf RI is expected to contribute to strengthening economic resilience for quality and equitable growth. To make it happen, Kemenparekraf/Baparekraf concretely contributes to priority programs to increase economic resources' carrying capacity and quality as a modality for sustainable economic development.

Table 1. Number of Employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment

Work unit	Number of Employees
Deputy Secretary for Industry and Investment	43
Directorate of Industrial Management	32
Directorate of Investment Management	24
Directorate of Business Standardization and Certification	26
Directorate of Access to Finance	40
Total	165

Source: Employee data of the Deputy for Industry and Investment 2022

The number of employees above consists of 102 Civil Servants (PNS), 19 Candidates for Civil Servants (CPNS 2022), and 44 Non-Permanent Employees (PTT). In accordance with the Ministry of Empowerment of State Civil Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform or Kemenpan RB in 2023, honorary workers (PTT) may no longer be in Government Agencies. This policy is in accordance with Government Regulation or PP Number 49 of 2018 concerning the Management of Government Employees with Work Agreements. In the regulation, non-PNS employees in government agencies still carry out their duties for a maximum of five years when the regulation is enacted.

Table 2. Data on Leadership Training for Echelon II, III, and IV employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment

Position	Leadership Training (person)	No Leadership Training (person)
Deputy Secretary and Director	3	1
Head of Section and Coordinator	13	1
Head of Sub Division/Sub Coordinator	12	16
Total	28	18

Source: Education and training data of the Deputy for Industry and Investment 2022

Officials within the Deputy for Industry and Investment, based on table 1.2, generally show that for the Leadership Training for Heads of Sub Divisions/Sub Coordinators within the Deputy for Industry and Investment. There is still not 50% who conduct training due to bureaucratic reasons, and the age of employees who are almost retirees do not qualify for leadership training. In addition,

for female structural officials to take care of children and husbands, there is no motivation from the employees themselves because they feel comfortable in their current positions. It is supported by the study results conducted by Ananta (2020). Motivation is very important in developing the competence and quality of employees because motivation can be an impetus for employees to work better, in line with the opinions of Armstrong (1998), which states that employees' dissatisfaction with their work can be motivated them to work better.

Furthermore, for ASN employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment, it is also necessary to develop competency training because, in this case, based on information from ASN staff at the technical directorate, no one has conducted tourism training, and some technical training conducted by employees is not in accordance with the placement because the work unit does not yet have competent employees, for example, for the placement of Commitment Making Officers and Assistant Expenditure Treasurers are still placed in the technical directorate where employees in the Secretariat should fill these positions. In Fiscal Year 2022, Kemenparekraf/Baparekraf will carry out PPPK recruitment to meet the needs of ASN as well as a form of employee recruitment for Non-Permanent Employees (PTT) to continue working at Kemenparekraf/Baparekraf through PPPK recruitment. This will have an impact on the Deputy for Industry and Investment, both for PTT employees themselves and for work productivity, because many employees will be dismissed if they do not pass the selection.

Based on the above, employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment need to prepare a task transfer strategy by improving the quality of their PTT employees and ASN employees. According to the results of interviews with stakeholders at the Deputy for Industry and Investment, the quality of employees is still low. This can be seen from the history of education that has not been qualified according to graph 1.1. it can be seen that there are still employees who graduate from junior high and high school, work experience in industry and investment is still not much, there are many impromptu and urgent jobs, and the number of employees is not adequate, and there are frequent changes and changes in leadership. This makes the quality employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment still less qualified,

Graph 1. Employee Education Data at the Deputy for Industry and Investment

Source: Data processed by Researchers (2022)

The implementation of rotating work entry with the covid-19 pandemic resulted in some employees who were WFO (Work From Office), and there were also employees who were WFH (Work From Home). This does not interfere with the program design or the tasks of the Deputy for Industry

and Investment because previously, such planning has been carried out regarding the things and programs to be carried out in the next year. With the Covid-19 pandemic condition, where the duties and functions of the Deputy for Industry and Investment are increasing, it does not make the habits of the ASN (State Civil Apparatus) in these institutions change in terms of work discipline, awareness, and concern for work which is still lacking.

The success or failure of an employee is determined by whether or not the competence possessed by the field of work is appropriate. However, what happened to the Deputy for Industry and Investment found that the factor causing the low performance of the previous strategic plan period was generally due to the low capacity and capability of the human resources of the apparatus. This can be proven through the results of interviews conducted by researchers with employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment; namely, several employees cannot operate computers and less critical employees or initiative when conducting program meetings in discussing future program designs or meetings. Evaluation is still lacking in terms of communicating and understanding the program's concept from the agency, so they do not have the competence to become presenters or speakers when conducting technical guidance, socialization, and counseling. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the duties and functions of the Deputy for Industry and Investment have increased. This also affects the increase in the work carried out by employees in the agency, with the increase in tasks followed by the lack of quality human resources, making the work overload/workload. Therefore, employees find it difficult to balance their work. This also affects the increase in the work carried out by employees in the agency, with the increase in tasks followed by the lack of quality human resources, making the work overload/workload. Therefore, employees find it difficult to balance their work. This also affects the increase in the work carried out by employees in the agency, with the increase in tasks followed by the lack of quality human resources, making the work overload/workload. Therefore, employees find it difficult to balance their work.

The increasingly high workload at the Deputy for Industry and Investment is also due to the inadequate number of employee needs and several employees who retire every year so that each employee must be able to hold other jobs, as shown in table 2. the number of employee needs in the Deputy for Industry and Investment with a comparison of the current condition of employees. Therefore, employees are asked to work optimally to achieve the agency's program targets or objectives.

Table 3. Projection of Employee Needs in the Future Deputy for Industry and Investment based on Employee Needs Based on Workload Analysis (ABK)

Work unit	Current number of employees (org)	Employee Needs to be Based on ABK (org)
Deputy Secretary for Industry and Investment	43	60
Directorate of Industrial Management	32	46
Directorate of Investment Management	24	37
Directorate of Business Standardization and Certification	26	60
Directorate of Access to Finance	40	43
Total	165	246

Source: Data processed by Researchers (2022)

The results of the researcher's interview showed there is a lot of urgent and impromptu work that the Deputy must complete for Industry and Investment. It is also supported by the data from the initial survey of researchers to employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment to determine the factors that affect the quality of employees by distributing them to 50 (fifty) respondents.

Table 4. Results of the Preliminary Survey of Factors Affecting Employee Quality Deputy for Industry and Investment

Variable	Statement	Percentage of Answers (%)	
		Yes	Not
Job Responsibilities	Employees do a job seriously and are ready to accept the risk.	47.4	52.6
Cooperation with Colleagues	Employees have the ability to work together towards a common vision and mission	84.2	15.8
Perform tasks according to the Job Description	Employees do the work according to the task (focus on one job)	63.2	36.8
Employee Initiative	Employees are willing to do work without having to be ordered or asked by superiors	47.4	52.6
Training	The training I got was very useful in improving my abilities and skills	57.9	42.1
Motivation	I enjoy my job	63.2	36.8

Source: Data processed by researchers (2022)

Teamwork can also be defined as teamwork, where a group of individuals collaborates with each other on tasks and responsibilities in order to get an output that has been decided together. The existence of good teamwork can improve cooperation and communication between internal and external stakeholders of the organization. Increasing the cohesiveness of teamwork in a work unit will result in an increase in employee work motivation because its members will indirectly create a good working atmosphere so that it is triggered to work better so that it can continuously improve the ability or quality of human resources in order to achieve organizational goals (Suhardi, 2020). This is also supported by research conducted by Weniawati et al., (2021) and Munir & Riyadi (2016).

According to Anita et al. (2013), the workload positively and significantly influences work motivation. It means that the higher the employee's workload, the higher the employee's work motivation, so it is necessary to have a clear description and determination of job descriptions so that each employee does not have multiple jobs. Giving them a higher workload and motivation makes them able to give their best performance at work. The results of the research also support this by Ningsih et al. (2017) and Adinugroho (2017). Employee productivity and performance are the results of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2011). Qualified and professional employees must have high work motivation toward their organization. The higher the work motivation, employees will try to work better because the task of the organization is not only to recruit employees but also to try to foster better employees, develop their abilities, regulate how to work, provide compensation, motivate and create a comfortable work environment so that employees are able to do their work. Tasks optimally in accordance with the duties and responsibilities (Lawler III, 1973)

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Work motivation is a psychological encouragement for employees to behave and work diligently according to the tasks and obligations are given (SP Robbins et al., 2013). Work motivation is also a success factor in achieving an organizational goal because whether or not an organizational goal is achieved is caused by employees who have good work motivation. Organizations must continue to motivate their employees to have positive work motivation. If employees already feel demotivated or do not have work motivation, it will be difficult for the organization to achieve organizational goals, and it has an impact on other employees. Furthermore, the survey results in table 1.4 show that motivation is also one of the variables that affect the improvement of the quality of employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment. This is in line with the opinion expressed by Robbins et al. (2013) and Maehr & Braskamp (1986). Improving the performance of a team that lacks quality will also have an impact on not creating a sense of belonging to the organization by having an impact on decreasing employee motivation in the organization, and the perceived workload continues to increase by employees due to incompatibilities with assignments from agencies that exceed work standards, making employees not can survive and work optimally in the agency. Based on the description above, the researcher realizes that it is important to examine the quality of human resources, work motivation, teamwork involvement, and workload more deeply. The low quality of human resources and work motivation of employees will lead to a lack of self-awareness of work behavior which also affects the effectiveness of employees' work. It is feared that it will affect the quality of human resources and the high workload of employees. Therefore, researchers want to know how much influence teamwork and workload have on the quality of human resources through employee organizational commitment. Therefore, the researcher intends to conduct further research on "The Influence of Team Work and Workload on the Quality of Human Resources Mediated by Work Motivation (Study on Employees of the Deputy for Industry and Investment of the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy)

2. Materials and Methods

This study analyzes the effect of teamwork on the quality of human resources and workload on the quality of human resources through work motivation as a mediation. This study explains the influence and influence relationship of the variables to be studied. This study uses a quantitative approach to analyze the relationship between variables because the data is expressed by numbers or a numerical scale (Prof. Dr. Suliyanto, SE, 2017). Sources of data used in this study consisted of primary and secondary sources. Furthermore, when viewed in terms of data collection methods or techniques in this study, namely by questionnaires, observations, and literature studies. Data collection aims to obtain data related to research.

3. Results and Discussions

Results

After performing the PLS algorithm and bootstrap using SmartPLS 3.0, hypothesis testing can be carried out to test whether the proposed hypothesis is supported or not. Researchers tested the hypothesis by measuring the direct effect, which can be seen in the path coefficient and indirect effect, to see the effect of the intervening variables in this study.

1) Direct Effect

Table 5. Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1_Teamwork -> Y_Quality of Human Resources	0.346	0.354	0.072	4,825	0.000
X1_Teamwork -> Z_Work Motivation	0.288	0.299	0.074	3,889	0.000
X2_Workload -> Y_Quality of Human Resources	-0.339	-0.334	0.072	4,733	0.000
X2_Workload -> Z_Work Motivation	-0.517	-0.503	0.080	6,476	0.000
Z_Work Motivation -> Y_Quality of Human Resources	0.338	0.333	0.069	4,898	0.000

Source: Data processed using SmartPLS 3.0 (2022)

H1: The influence of teamwork on the quality of human resources

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, table 5 above shows the original sample value of 0.346 on teamwork on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a positive influence on the teamwork variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, the t statistic value is also shown 4,825 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that teamwork has a significant direct effect on the quality of human resources. Therefore, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H2: The Effect of Teamwork on Work Motivation

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above shows the original sample value of 0.288 on Teamwork to Work Motivation. This means that there is a positive influence on the Teamwork variable on the Work Motivation variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 3.889 and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that the Teamwork variable has a significant direct effect on the Work Motivation variable. Therefore, it can be concluded that the second hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H3: The effect of workload on the quality of human resources

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, table 5 above shows the original sample value of -0.339 on the workload on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a negative effect on the workload variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, the t statistic value is also shown 4,733 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that the workload significantly directly affects the quality of human resources. Therefore, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H4: The effect of workload on work motivation

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 5 above shows the original sample value of -0.517 on the workload on work motivation. This means there is a negative effect on the workload variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, the t statistic value is also shown as 6,476 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05) which means that the workload has a significant direct effect on work motivation. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H5: The influence of motivation on the quality of human resources

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient, table 5 above shows the original sample value of 0.338 on work motivation on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a positive influence on the work motivation variable on the quality of human resources. In addition, the t statistic value is also shown as 4,898 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that work motivation has a significant direct effect on the quality of human resources. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

2) Indirect Effect

Table 6. Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1_Teamwork -> Z_Work Motivation -> Y_Quality of Human Resources	0.097	0.100	0.033	2,960	0.003
X2_Workload -> Z_Work Motivation -> Y_Quality of Human Resources	-0.175	-0.169	0.050	3,483	0.001

Source: Data processed using Smart PLS 3.0 (2022)

H6: Teamwork on the Quality of Human Resources through Work Motivation

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 6, the teamwork variable affects the quality of human resources, with work motivation acting as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is 0.097, which means that there is a positive influence on the effect of teamwork on the quality of human resources with work motivation as a mediator. Then, the t-statistic value is 2.960, and the p-value is 0.006 (<0.05), which means that the teamwork variable has a significant indirect effect on the quality of human resources, with work

motivation acting as a mediator. Therefore, it is concluded that the sixth hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

H7: Workload on the Quality of Human Resources through Work Motivation

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 6, the workload variable affects the quality of human resources, with work motivation acting as a mediator between the two. The original sample value of the influence of the three variables is -0.175, which means that there is a negative influence in influence of workload on the quality of human resources with work motivation as a mediator. Then, the value of the t statistic is 3.483, and the p-value is 0.001 (< 0.05), which means that the workload variable has a significant indirect effect on the quality of human resources, with work motivation acting as a mediator. Therefore, it is concluded that the seventh hypothesis in this study is accepted and statistically supported by the results of this study.

Discussions

The results of the description of respondents based on age indicate that the average age characteristics of employees who work in the Deputy for Industry and Investment are in the productive age, namely 31-40 years. Respondents based on this age are divided into four (4) sections, namely the age of 21-30 years, as many as 36 respondents or 30.8 percent of the total, 31-40 years, as many as 50 respondents or 42.7 percent of the total, ages 41-50 years as many as 21 respondents or 17.9 percent of the total and aged over 51 years as many as ten respondents or 8.5 percent of the total.

Respondents based on gender indicate that employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment for the number of respondents with male gender are 58 respondents or 49.6 percent, and female sex are 59 women, or 50.4 percent. There is no difference between the number of male and female respondents who work as the Deputy for Industry and Investment. Furthermore, respondents based on education are mostly with D3 educational background, as many as ten people or 8.5 percent, for respondents who have an S1/D4 education level, as many as 87 respondents or 74.4 percent, S2 education levels are 18 respondents or 15.5 percent and doctoral education as many as two people or 1.7 percent. Furthermore, respondents based on length of work were dominated by employees with a length of work between 1-5 years as many as 44 respondents or 37.6 percent and respondents who had a length of work of 5-10 years as many as 44 respondents or 37.6 percent, than respondents who had a length of work above 10-20 years as many as 17 respondents or 14.5 percent and the last respondent with a length of work above 21 years as many as 12 respondents or 10.3 percent. As for the respondent's data based on marital status, who are married, as many as 81 respondents or 69.2 percent, and respondents who are not married, as many as 36 or 30.8 percent. Five percent and lastly, 12 respondents or 10.3 percent of respondents with a length of work over 21 years. As for the respondent's data, based on marital status, they have married as many as 81 respondents or 69.2 percent, and respondents who are not married, as many as 36, or 30.8 percent. Five percent and lastly, 12 respondents or 10.3 percent of respondents with a length of work over 21 years. As for the respondent's data based on marital status, who are married, as many as 81 respondents or 69.2 percent, and respondents who are not married, as many as 36 or 30.8 percent.

The Direct Effect of Teamwork on the Quality of Human Resources

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 5 above shows the original sample value of 0.346 on teamwork on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a positive influence on the teamwork variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 4.825, and the p-value is 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that teamwork directly affects the quality of human resources. This can explain that with successful and effective teamwork in the Deputy for Industry and Investment, the work will be completed properly, and the quality of the employees will be achieved well.

According to Sanyal & Hisam (2018) that teamwork has a clear and significant relationship to the quality of productivity and work performance of employees in the workplace, so the success of teamwork depends on the synergy that exists among all team members, which creates an environment where all employees are willing to contribute and participate in promoting a team environment positive and effective. Teamwork is one of the determinants of the success of an organization because it can improve organizational performance; teamwork is one of the soft skills that must be possessed by every employee (Sutisna, 2019).

Research conducted by Sholihin et al. (2017) Building a company requires a strong vision as the foundation and teamwork as the pillar to achieve business targets. Thus, it must be admitted that teamwork influences the company's progress. The more solid the teamwork formed, the greater the chance of success. In addition, Hackman (1987) also states that factors in building solid teamwork are related to some aspects. They provide evaluations and rewards, social relationships to solve internal conflicts, organizational support, clear tasks and goals, an organizational environment, and leaders who are useful for facilitating team interaction are needed to create a Successful team.

Teamwork can also help the HR division manage policies, ranging from learning, and development, to workplace culture. However, they all have an impact on the success of the organization. Previous research that has been carried out by Prabawa & Supartha (2018) increasing teamwork can be done by forming a good team such as the need to increase closeness and bonds between employees so as to create a sense of mutual help and support in the work team to achieve company goals. Building a company requires a strong vision as the foundation, and teamwork as the pillar to achieve business targets. The progress of the company is influenced by the teamwork in it. The more solid the teamwork that is formed, the greater the chance of success (Sholihin et al., 2017). The work team in the organization, if it is not optimal and cannot work together well, will be able to hamper and experience obstacles in carrying out work activities.

Maintaining team collaboration and building a solid team is important for a company. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Sutisna (2019), Sholihin et al. (2017), Hackman (1987), Sanyal & Hisam (2018), Prabawa & Supartha (2018), Hanaysha (2016) and Sepnatika (2021). The work team in the organization, if it is not optimal and cannot work together well, will be able to hamper and experience obstacles in carrying out work activities. So maintaining team collaboration and building a solid team is important for a company. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Sutisna (2019), Sholihin et al. (2017), Hackman (1987), Sanyal & Hisam (2018), Prabawa & Supartha (2018), Hanaysha (2016) and Sepnatika (2021). The work team in the organization, if it is not optimal and cannot work together well, will be able to hamper and experience obstacles in carrying out work activities. So maintaining team collaboration and building a solid team is important for a company. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Sutisna (2019), Sholihin et al. (2017), Hackman (1987), Sanyal & Hisam (2018), Prabawa & Supartha (2018), Hanaysha (2016) and Sepnatika (2021).

The Direct Effect of Teamwork on Work Motivation

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in the table above shows the original sample value of 0.288 on Teamwork to Work Motivation. This means that there is a positive influence on the Teamwork variable on the Work Motivation variable. In addition, it is also shown that the t-statistic value is 3.889 and the p-value is 0.000 (<0.05), which means that the Teamwork variable directly affects the Work Motivation variable.

Based on the results of the study, the indicator that has the highest score on teamwork is "Communicating well between employees so that there are no misunderstandings in working together," and the highest score on the indicator of work motivation is "Salary and benefits can provide encouragement to work better." That is, the higher the teamwork of employees will increase their work motivation. With this increase in influence, it can be conveyed that there is good communication between employees on a job that results from daily involvement in the hope that the increase in salaries and allowances will give the organization an appreciation that can encourage them to work better.

By providing targets, employees will feel challenged (Julianto et al., 2021). It opens up opportunities for all employees to develop and achieve, which can be improved through teamwork so that difficult jobs can be completed easily. This is in line with Astuti's (2021) research, which states that motivation in a work team comes from within each individual but can also be given by the team or division leader, either in the form of greeting, appreciation, or appreciation. The researcher interviewed several employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment and the Leaders in each work unit. The Deputy for Industry and Investment has high motivation if a job or follow-up disposition is completed in a team because this reduces miscommunication from all parties. The existence of a good teamwork attitude in the Deputy for Industry and Investment will be able to complement each other to achieve the expected goals of the organization. This is also in line with the opinion of Hutagalung (2008). together effectively and efficiently.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Julianto et al. (2021), Astuti (2021), Hutagalung (2008), Suhardi (2020), Tyas & Rizki (2021), Jungert et al. (2018), Kelemba et al. (2017), Jin (1993), Yusianto & Melinda (2015) and Setiyani et al. (2019).

The Direct Effect of Workload on the Quality of Human Resources

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 5 above shows the original sample value of -0.339 on the workload on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a negative effect on the workload variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, the t statistic value is also shown 4,733 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that the workload significantly directly affects the quality of human resources.

Based on the highest indicator on the workload variable, namely "The tasks that are always given are sometimes sudden in a short period of time," and the highest value on the human resource quality indicator is "regular human resource training is important in the organization". This means that the higher the workload carried out by employees, the quality of the self will be less than optimal. With assignments that are always impromptu and in a short period of time, it is also necessary to always be provided with training to increase the competence and skills of each employee.

In line with the results of research conducted by Marzban et al. (2016), reducing the workload will be beneficial for maintenance personnel, and a high workload is one of the most important factors of decreasing employee quality, which can be reduced through good organization and planning. A high workload statistically has a lower quality of life effect than employees with a normal workload.

The Effect of Teamwork and Workload on The Quality of Human Resources Mediated by Work Motivation
(I Purnamati, D Susita, CW Wolor)

The research of Sjöberg et al. (2020) also show that interventions aimed at increasing social support can reduce work-related illnesses. This means that a high workload affects the health of employees.

In line with the research presented by Anita, Julia Aziz, Nasir Yunus (2013), it shows that workload can significantly improve employee performance. It means that the more workloads given, the more difficult it is for employees to improve their performance. The results of research also support this by Rolos et al., (2018) that workload has a negative effect on employee performance, meaning that if the workload increases, it will reduce the potential for employee performance. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Musdalifah & Achnes (2017), Mahawati et al. (2021), Marzban et al. (2016), Sjöberg et al. (2020), Anita, Julia Aziz, Nasir Yunus (2013) and Rolos et al., (2018).

The Direct Effect of Workload on Work Motivation

Based on the statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 5 above, it shows the original sample value of -0.517 on workload on work motivation. This means that there is a negative effect on the workload variable on the human resource quality variable. In addition, the t statistic value of is also shown 6,476 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05) which means that the workload has a significant direct effect on work motivation.

According to the results of research conducted by Anita, Julia Aziz, Nasir Yunus (2013) that workload has a positive and significant effect on work motivation. However, this is different from the results of research conducted by Kusumaningtyas (2018) which states that workload and work motivation have a negative relationship, meaning that the heavier the workload, the lower the employee's work motivation and vice versa, the less workload, the higher the employee's work motivation. Previous research has also shown that workload has a negative and significant effect on work motivation. An excessive workload can cause a decrease in enthusiasm and motivation so it becomes one of the causes of work fatigue (Semaksiani et al., 2019).

The Deputy for Industry and Investment monitors the work carried out in each of his work units and makes a checklist system which is monitored by the Deputy Secretariat Team, where this checklist is used to remind and monitor the follow-up to the Minister's directives that have been carried out and not. The hope of making this checklist makes it easier for employees and reduces the buildup of the workload of employees who will be in the work unit because they prioritize work that is urgent and urgent and that requires an immediate deadline. Optimization in the workplace must always be applied by all employees in the workplace, but sometimes some employees feel that they are too burdened with the work they do so that it affects their motivation to work. The results of this study are different from the results of previous studies Hariyono et al. (2012) showed that the positive workload perception is that the workload is a work challenge and motivates them to work better for themselves and their organization. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Kusumaningtyas (2018) and (Semaksiani et al., 2019).

The Direct Effect of Work Motivation on the Quality of Human Resources

The statistical analysis of the path coefficient in table 5 above shows the original sample value of 0.338 on work motivation on the quality of human resources. This means that there is a positive influence on the work motivation variable on the quality of human resources. In addition, the t statistic value of is also shown 4,898 and p values of 0.000 (< 0.05), which means that work motivation has a significant direct effect on the quality of human resources.

Based on the research results, the indicator that has the highest value on the work motivation variable is "Salary and benefits can encourage to work better" and the indicator on the quality of human resources is "regular human resource training is important in the organization." This means that the motivation to work for employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment is high by providing better welfare which will later be used as a race to encourage employees to learn, increase knowledge, competence and capability so that with the knowledge possessed, competence and capability increase then The quality of employees will also increase.

In line with research conducted by Moore et al. (2010) and Dew (2009) show that work motivation has a positive effect on the quality of human resources, because motivation is a driving and motivating actor in learning to increase knowledge, competence, and capability. According to Harrell & Stahl (1984), Achievement motivation embedded in the work system according to individual needs and desires is able to produce greater individual performance improvements. According to Werdhiastutie et al. (2020) the intended work motivation encourages improvement elements that will be implemented and evaluated as a step in improving the quality of the organization's human resources. This study is in line with Muazza's (2021) research and Menshikova et al.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Werdhiastutie et al. (2020), Moore et al. (2010), Dew (2009), Harrell & Stahl (1984), Muazza (2021) and Menshikova et al. (2020).

Indirect Effect of Teamwork on the Quality of Human Resources through Work Motivation

The results showed that the effect of teamwork on the quality of human resources through work motivation was positive and significant by showing the effect of work motivation on employees of the Deputy for Industry and Investment being able to mediate the effect of teamwork on the quality of human resources. So that the hypothesis H6 in this study is declared accepted. This shows that the existence of good teamwork within the Deputy for Industry and Investment can affect the quality of human resources by being mediated by work motivation because when teamwork is carried out well it will motivate employees to perform tasks as much as possible and build a high sense of attachment to employees. and ultimately will continue to trigger continuous learning in improving the quality of each employee.

Harmonious research also conducted by Prabawa & Supartha (2018) shows that partially teamwork has a positive effect on employee productivity, because teamwork in order to continue to maintain behavior needs to have mutual respect and have good relations with superiors and co-workers in order to create a solid team that will eventually become complementary to achieve organizational goals (Tyas & Rizki, nd). Work teams formed voluntarily have higher work motivation and better performance compared to work teams assigned by superiors (Jin, 1993). Setiyani et al. (2019) state that effective teamwork can encourage employees to carry out tasks with better results. Thus, when work motivation increases, it will eventually form a solid teamwork in building a high sense of attachment to employees, so that employees in the team will continue to learn and learn in improving the quality within themselves.

Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Sholihin et al. (2017), Julianto et al. (2021), Astuti (2021), Prabawa & Supartha (2018) and Setiyani et al. (2019).

Indirect Effect of Workload on the Quality of Human Resources through Work Motivation

The results showed that the effect of workload on the quality of human resources through work motivation was negative and significant by showing the effect of work motivation on employees of the Deputy for Industry and Investment being able to mediate the effect of workload on the quality of human resources. So that the hypothesis H7 in this study is declared accepted. This shows that the existence of a high workload within the Deputy for Industry and Investment can affect the decline in the quality of human resources mediated by work motivation because the provision of a high workload will reduce employee motivation to continue their work so that it can affect the quality of the employee.

The harmonized study conducted by Ferava et al. (2021) that workload does not directly affect employee performance, but workload can affect performance through work motivation because workload has a significant effect on work motivation and work motivation has a significant effect on improving the quality of human resources. In addition, the results of Arifin et al. (2016) show that workload has an insignificant and negative effect on employee performance, meaning that an increase in workload will decrease employee performance although it is not significant. Based on this description, the results of this study are relevant to the results of research conducted by Silaban et al. (2021), Ferava et al. (2021) and Arifin et al. (2016).

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and hypothesis testing in the discussion presented, several conclusions can be obtained as follows:

1. Teamwork positively affects the quality of employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment. This means that the higher the teamwork, the higher the quality of the employees. On the other hand, if teamwork is low, then the quality of employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment is also low. Based on research results, teamwork can also help the HR division manage policies, ranging from learning, development, to workplace culture. however, they all have an impact on the success of the organization. This is due to the establishment of solid teamwork related to the provision of evaluation and rewards, social relations to solve internal conflicts, organizational support, clear tasks and goals, organizational environment, and useful leaders to facilitate team interaction needed to create a successful team.
2. Teamwork positively affects employee motivation at the Deputy for Industry and Investment. That is, the more effective teamwork will increase employee motivation. With this increase in influence, strong cooperation is motivated due to high teamwork spirit. Teamwork ensures workplace democracy, drives change, encourages innovation and creativity, and enables effective decision-making and networking. the existence of strong teamwork will motivate employees' work because by providing targets, employees will feel challenged so that it opens up opportunities for all employees to develop and achieve, which in the end can be improved through teamwork so that difficult jobs can be completed easily.
3. Workload has a negative effect on the quality of employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment. Employees with a low workload will bring out their optimal self-quality, whereas those with a high workload will produce low self-quality. There is a link between workload and improving the quality of employees, where the higher the workload received by an employee will affect the quality of the employee in completing his work, because the level of focus and concentration is low so that it will have an impact on the performance of the employee.
4. Workload has a negative effect on employee motivation in the Deputy for Industry and

Investment. This means that employees with a low workload will lead to high work motivation, whereas employees with a high workload will bring up low work motivation. This happens when a high workload is not accompanied by an increase in income or employee rewards. In addition, excessive workload can cause a decrease in morale and motivation so that it becomes one of the causes of work fatigue so that the motivation to complete the task will decrease.

5. Work motivation on the quality of human resources positively affects employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment. That is, the higher work motivation has an impact on the quality of the employee's self, which will increase and be optimal. That is, if the motivation is lost from the employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment, it will have a great influence and impact on the sustainability of an organization because high work motivation will improve the quality of employees.
6. Teamwork positively affects the quality of human resources, with work motivation as a mediating variable for employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment. Employees of the Deputy for Industry and Investment who have high teamwork will have an impact on their optimal quality through high work motivation as well as on the employee. It means The existence of strong teamwork will motivate employees' work because by providing targets, employees will feel challenged so that it opens up opportunities for all employees to develop and achieve, which in the end can be improved through teamwork so that difficult jobs can be completed easily.
7. Workload has a negative effect on the quality of human resources with work motivation as a mediating variable for employees at the Deputy for Industry and Investment. Employees of the Deputy for Industry and Investment who have a high workload will have an impact on their quality which is less than optimal from their work motivation, on the other hand employees in the Deputy for Industry and Investment who have a low workload will have an impact on their optimal quality supported by work motivation of each employee.

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References

- Adinugroho, J. (2017). The effect of workload on work motivation at Cahaya Mas Restaurant.
- Anggoro, B. (2017). The quality of ASN is still low. Indonesian media.
- Anita, Julia Aziz, Nasir Yunus, M. (2013). The Effect of Placement and Workload on Work Motivation and Its Impact on Work Performance of the Manpower Service Employees and the Mobility of the Acehnese Population. *Management*, Volume 2., <https://doi.org/ISSN 2302-0199>
- Anita, J., Aziz, N., & Yunus, M. (2013). The effect of placement and workload on work motivation and its impact on the work performance of the labor service employees and the mobility of the Acehnese population. *Syiah Kuala University Postgraduate Management Journal*, 2(1), 67–77.
- Arifin, MZ, Alhabsji, T., & Utami, HN (2016). The Effect of Workload and Compensation on Organizational Commitment in Efforts to Improve Employee Performance (Study on Executive Level Employees of Perum Jasa Tirta I Brantas River Basin and Bengawan Solo). *Journal of Business and Management*, 3(2).

- Astuti, AS (2021). The Role of Teamwork, Work Environment, Compensation System in an Effort to Increase Employee Extrinsic Motivation at the Dompnet Dhuafa Integrated Health Hospital. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(1), 182–188.
- Dew, R. (2009). Creative resolve response: How changes in creative motivation relate to cognitive style. *Journal of Management Development*.
- Ferava, F., Anindita, R., & Hilmy, MR (2021). The Motivation as A Mediation Relationship of Work Load Performance in Medical Record Staff at X Hospital. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic*, 5(2), 137–142.
- Hackman, JR (1987). The design of work teams. *handbook of Organizational Behavior*, ed. JW Lorsch. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Harrell, AM, & Stahl, MJ (1984). McClelland's trichotomy of needs theory and the job satisfaction and work performance of CPA firm professionals. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 9(3–4), 241–252.
- HUTAGALUNG, PR (2008). The effect of employee perceptions of teamwork, compensation, leadership on organizational commitment at PT Arion Paramita Holding Company. Gadjah Mada University.
- Julianto, D., Gunawan, K., & Sudiarditha, IK (2021). The Role of Team Collaboration and Supervision on Auditor Performance: Work Motivation as Mediation. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 20, 1–12.
- Kelemba, J., Chepkilot, R., & Zakayo, C. (2017). Influence of teamwork practices on employee performance in public service in Kenya. *African Research Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 1–9.
- Kusumaningtyas, IT (2018). The Relationship Between Workload And Work Motivation On Employees Of Pt. X. Mercu Buana University Jakarta.
- Lawler III, EE (1973). *Motivation in work organizations*.
- Maehr, ML, & Braskamp, LA (1986). *The motivation factor: A theory of personal investment*. Lexington Books/DC Heath and Com.
- Mangkunegara, AAP (2011). *Company human resource management*.
- Marzban, S., Najafi, M., Asefzadeh, S., Gholami, S., & Rajaei, R. (2016). Effect of workload on quality of work life among staff of the teaching hospitals of Shahid Beheshti University of Medical Sciences (2014). *Journal of Inflammatory Diseases*, 20(1), 63–69.
- Menshikova, OI, Stukanova, SS, & Stukanova, IP (2020). Innovative Motivation as a Factor of Improving the Quality of Human Resources and the Development of Socio-economic Systems. In *Complex Systems: Innovation and Sustainability in the Digital Age* (pp. 11–17). Springer.
- Moore, LL, Grabsch, DK, & Rotter, C. (2010). Using achievement motivation theory to explain student participation in a residential leadership learning community. *Journal of Leadership Education*, 9(2), 22–34.
- Muazza, M. (2021). In Search of Quality Human Resources in Education: Professional Competency, Compensation, Working Climate, and Motivation toward Vocational Teachers' Performance. *Indonesian Research Journal in Education| IRJE|*, 5(1), 175–191.
- Munir, M., & Riyadi, S. (2016). The Influence of Individual Characteristics, Self Efficacy and Team Work on Commitment and Productivity of Health Cadres in Tuban Regency, East Java Province. *JADE17: Doctoral Journal of Economics*, 1(1).
- Ningsih, S., Alwie, AF, & Fitri, K. (2017). The Influence of Work Saturation, Workload, and Work Conflict on the Work Motivation of Nurses at RSUD DR. RM. Pratomo Bagan Readiapi Rokan Hilir Regency. Riau University.
- Prabawa, IMA, & Supartha, IWG (2018). Increase employee productivity through empowerment, teamwork and training in service companies. *Unud Management E-Journal*, 7(1), 497–524.

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- Prabu, A. (2005). The effect of motivation on job satisfaction of employees of the National Family Planning Coordinating Board in Muara Enim Regency. *Sriwijaya Journal of Management & Business*, 3(6), 1–25.
- Prof. Dr. Suliyanto, SE, M. (2017). *Quantitative Research Methods. Research Methodology Training*.
- Robbins, SP, Judge, TA, & Brito, JE (2013). *Comportamiento organizacional*. Pearson educacion Naucalpan.
- Rolos, JKR, Sambul, SAP, & Rumawas, W. (2018). The effect of workload on employee performance at PT. Asuransi Jiwasraya Manado City Branch. *Journal of Business Administration (JAB)*, 6(004), 19–27.
- Sanyal, S., & Hisam, MW (2018). The impact of teamwork on work performance of employees: A study of faculty members at Dhofar University. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 20(3), 15–22.
- Sepnatika, TU (2021). *The Influence of Teamwork, Work Environment and Workload on Work Performance of Employees of the Palembang City Archives and Library Office*. 021008-Universitas Tridianti.
- Sholihin, A., Amboningtyas, D., Hasiholan, LB, & Fathoni, A. (2017). The Effect of Compensation And Team Work On Employee Work Productivity Through Employee Loyalty In Cv. Semarang Rose. *Journal of Management*, 3(3).
- Silaban, RL, Handaru, AW, & Saptono, A. (2021). Effect of Workload, Competency, and Career Development on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment Intervening Variables. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSSW)*, 3(01), 294–311.
- Sjöberg, A., Pettersson-Strömbäck, A., Sahlén, K.-G., Lindholm, L., & Norström, F. (2020). The burden of high workload on the health-related quality of life among home care workers in Northern Sweden. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 93(6), 747–764.
- Suhardi, M. (2020). The Influence of Team Work and Organizational Learning on the Organizational Commitment of State Junior High School Principals in Mataram City. *Visionary Journal: Research and Development in the Field of Educational Administration*, 4(2).
- Sutisna, G. (2019). *Analysis of Employee Teamwork at Pt Nusantara Cemerlang*. Proceedings of the Frima
- Tyas, AAWP, & Rizki, IL (ND). *The Impact of Work Engagement Through Work Motivation Seen From The Work Environment And Teamwork*.
- Weniawati, NK, Wulandari, NLAA, & Sunny, MP (2021). Effect of Financial Compensation, Teamwork and Organizational Commitment on VIP Employee Job Satisfaction. *Widya Amrita: Journal of Management, Entrepreneurship and Tourism*, 1(3), 897–908.
- Werdhiastutie, A., Suhariadi, F., & Partiw, SG (2020). Achievement Motivation as Antecedents of Quality Improvement of Organizational Human Resources. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal) Volume*, 3, 747–752.